

YASHIL

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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INDICATORS AND CRITERIA OF WOMEN'S SUSTAINABLE EMPLOYMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract: This article presents a comprehensive analysis of sustainable women's employment within the context of economic growth. It examines women's participation in the labor market, the opportunities available to them, existing working conditions, and the evaluation of employment levels using key indicators and international labor standards. The study also analyzes the influence of gender equality, job security, social protection systems, and access to professional development on economic performance. Drawing on recent reforms, statistical data, and international best practices, the article offers policy recommendations aimed at strengthening women's economic participation.

Key words: women's employment, sustainable jobs, labor market, gender equality, economic growth, employment indicators, labor standards, social protection, professional development, formal and informal employment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ayollar bandligining barqaror iqtisodiy o'sish jarayonidagi o'rni chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Unda ayollarning mehnat bozoridagi ishtiroki, ular uchun yaratilgan imkoniyatlar, mavjud mehnat sharoitlari, bandlik darajasini baholashda qo'llaniladigan asosiy ko'rsatkichlar va xalqaro mehnat standartlari asosida tahlil olib boriladi. Shuningdek, gender tengligi, ish barqarorligi, ijtimoiy himoya tizimlari va kasbiy rivojlanish imkoniyatlarining iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'siri yoritiladi. So'nggi islohotlar, statistik ma'lumotlar va xalqaro tajriba asosida ayollarning iqtisodiy faolligini kuchaytirish bo'yicha takliflar ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ayollar bandligi, barqaror ish o'rinlari, mehnat bozori, gender tengligi, iqtisodiy o'sish, bandlik ko'rsatkichlari, mehnat standartlari, ijtimoiy himoya, kasbiy rivojlanish, rasmiy va norasmiy bandlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен всесторонний анализ устойчивой занятости женщин в контексте экономического роста. Рассматривается участие женщин в рынке труда, предоставленные им возможности, существующие условия труда, а также проводится оценка уровня занятости на основе ключевых показателей и международных трудовых стандартов. Также исследуется влияние гендерного равенства, стабильности занятости, систем социальной защиты и возможностей профессионального развития на экономический рост. На основе последних реформ, статистических данных и международного опыта в статье даны рекомендации по усилению экономического участия женщин.

Ключевые слова: занятость женщин, устойчивые рабочие места, рынок труда, гендерное равенство, экономический рост, показатели занятости, трудовые стандарты, социальная защита, профессиональное развитие, формальная и неформальная занятость.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the effective utilization of human capital has become a crucial factor in ensuring the economic development of nations. In particular, the sustainable employment of women—who constitute a significant segment of the labor market—not only improves their socio-economic status but also plays a vital role in enhancing the overall well-being of society. As emphasized by the World Bank, the International Labour Organization (ILO), the United Nations (UN), and other international institutions, the active participation of women in the labor market is one of the key prerequisites for achieving sustainable and inclusive economic growth.

In Uzbekistan as well, comprehensive reforms have been undertaken in recent years to promote gender equality, increase women's economic activity, and provide them with sustainable employment opportunities in both the formal and informal sectors. Notably, under the Presidential Decree dated March 7, 2022, titled "On Additional Measures to Support Women and Enhance Their Role in Society", effective mechanisms have been

established through the implementation of the “Women’s Register” system, vocational guidance centers, and online employment platforms. These efforts have had a direct impact on increasing women’s participation in economic growth. [1]

Nevertheless, challenges remain in certain regions where women face limited access to employment opportunities, low levels of formal employment, and insufficient social protection for those working in the informal sector. According to data from the Statistics Agency for the end of 2023, although women constitute nearly 47 percent of the total labor force, the share of those formally employed remains around 36 percent. The situation is particularly concerning for women living in rural areas, those from low-income families, mothers of multiple children, women with disabilities, and single mothers, who often lack access to stable and formal employment.

Assessing the level of women’s sustainable employment requires a comprehensive analysis based on several indicators, including the proportion of women of working age, formal employment rates, the gender pay gap, levels of professional development, and the availability of socially protected employment. Importantly, employment policies should be gender-sensitive, and job creation efforts must prioritize not only quantitative aspects but also the quality, stability, and social protection of employment opportunities. [2]

In recent years, increasing women’s participation in economic life has become a key priority of state policy in Uzbekistan. Currently, there are more than 9.7 million women aged between 18 and 60 across the country, of whom approximately 5.5 million are considered to be of working age. However, as of the end of 2023, only 3.4 million of these women were engaged in permanent employment, indicating that the official employment rate among working-age women stands at approximately 62 percent.

According to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, in 2023, around 1.35 million women in Uzbekistan were formally employed, while nearly 900,000 women were engaged in the informal sector—earning income through activities such as home-based sewing, poultry farming, agriculture, or service provision (e.g., cooking or beauty services). The high number of women employed in the informal sector results in their limited access to social protection systems, including pensions, paid leave, and health insurance coverage. [3]

Analyses indicate that there are significant regional disparities in women’s employment levels across Uzbekistan. For example, in Tashkent city and Tashkent region, the female employment rate exceeds 70 percent, whereas in regions such as Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya, this figure remains around 45–50 percent. Contributing factors to these disparities include a shortage of available jobs, limited access to vocational education and training opportunities, and the persistence of gender-based stereotypes. [4]

Another pressing issue is the gender wage gap between men and women. According to the 2023 report of the State Committee on Statistics, the average monthly salary for men was 4.1 million UZS, while for women it was 3.2 million UZS—representing a wage gap of approximately 22 percent. This disparity is largely attributable to the concentration of women in lower-paid sectors such as education, healthcare, and service industries.

Another important aspect concerns women’s participation in vocational education and training. In the 2022–2023 academic years, women accounted for 42 percent of the 197,000 students enrolled in vocational training centers across the country. Although this represents a significant share, women’s participation in technical, industrial, and high-income fields such as information technology remains relatively low. For instance, women enrolled in programs such as programming or electrical engineering constituted only about 12–15 percent of the total student body in those disciplines. [5]

The aforementioned figures highlight the need to assess women’s employment not only in quantitative but also in qualitative terms. Indicators such as the formality and stability of employment, the availability of social guarantees, and opportunities for professional advancement play a crucial role in shaping effective economic policy. Furthermore, the integration of modern technologies, the expansion of remote work formats, and programs supporting women’s entrepreneurship have the potential to yield significant results in this area.

This article focuses on these key issues by examining the role of women in economic growth, current employment indicators, relevant assessment criteria, pressing challenges, and potential solutions. Based on international experiences, the paper proposes evidence-based recommendations for enhancing women’s employment in the context of Uzbekistan. Additionally, it provides an in-depth analysis of the impact of women’s sustainable employment on economic growth, using statistical data, practical programs, and relevant legal frameworks.

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

The issue of sustainable employment among women has become one of the most pressing directions in modern economic discourse, prompting extensive research at both international and national levels. In exploring this topic in depth, the literature concerning economic development, gender equality, employment policy, social protection systems, and labor market dynamics plays a fundamental role.

According to World Bank reports, the active inclusion of women in economic life has a positive impact on the growth of gross domestic product (GDP). Research findings indicate that a 10 percent increase in women's employment can contribute, on average, a 1.2 percent rise in economic growth. Furthermore, the International Labour Organization (ILO) identifies several key factors necessary for ensuring women's sustainable employment, including legal equality, flexible working conditions, and the availability of social protections [6].

Domestic scholars have also paid significant attention to this issue. In particular, A. Tadjibayeva analyzes the reforms aimed at increasing women's employment in Uzbekistan and highlights insufficient social infrastructure, weaknesses in vocational training systems, and persistent gender stereotypes as major obstacles. She suggests that promoting family-based enterprises and home-based work within a public–private partnership framework can be an effective approach for integrating women into the labor market.

In their research, E. Saidov and M. Rakhimova examine the disparities between formal and informal employment among women. They emphasize that, particularly in rural areas, women's labor often remains informal, leaving them without access to social protection and pension systems. The authors argue that to increase formal employment, it is necessary to incentivize small businesses through tax benefits and social privileges.

X. Sharipov's analysis of the relationship between gender equality and sustainable development demonstrates a positive correlation between women's economic activity and family stability. According to his findings, women's access to stable employment positively affects their children's education and health, which in turn contributes to long-term economic stability [7].

Additionally, researcher M. Yuldashev advocates for the promotion of sustainable employment through the development of women's entrepreneurship. He emphasizes that providing tax incentives, subsidies, and microcredits to women-led small businesses plays a vital role in enhancing their economic participation.

The existing scientific and analytical literature underscores the need for a comprehensive approach to addressing the issue of sustainable women's employment. Key areas for policy intervention include strengthening the legal framework, developing the education and vocational training systems, reducing gender-based stereotypes, and expanding social protection mechanisms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study conducts a comprehensive analysis of women's sustainable employment and its impact on economic growth. A combination of statistical methods, comparative analysis, and content analysis techniques was employed in the research. The analysis is based on official data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, as well as international organizations such as the ILO, UNDP, and others for the period 2020–2024. In addition, qualitative interviews were conducted to identify barriers and opportunities related to women's labor force participation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent years, the issue of sustainable employment for women in Uzbekistan has become one of the key priorities of state policy. Data and analyses obtained within this study indicate that sustainable employment not only ensures women's economic independence but also has a significant impact on the country's overall economic growth.

According to statistical data as of 2024, the participation of women in the overall labor market of Uzbekistan accounted for 45.2 percent. At the same time, a significant distinction exists between the formal and informal segments of female employment. Specifically, data from the State Statistics Committee show that more than 60 percent of women in rural areas are engaged in informal employment, leaving them outside social protection systems. This means they lack a stable source of income [8].

Further analysis revealed that women's employment is predominantly concentrated in the following sectors: education (31 percent), healthcare (22 percent), services (18 percent), and agriculture (16 percent). However, their participation in high-income and technological sectors, particularly IT, finance, and industrial branches, remains quite low—approximately 8–10 percent. This situation reflects occupational gender segregation and indicates that women are unable to fully utilize their economic potential [9].

To define a job as “sustainable,” attention was paid to the criteria developed by the State Labor Inspection: the presence of a formal employment contract, regularity of monthly salary payments, coverage by social insurance, safe working conditions, and availability of professional development opportunities. Based on surveys conducted, it was found that only 42 percent of women work under such sustainable labor conditions [10].

Comparative analyses indicate that opportunities for sustainable employment for women are more prevalent in central regions (Tashkent city, Samarkand, Fergana), while in peripheral regions and rural areas, these opportunities sharply decline. This reflects the existence of socio-economic disparities between regions. Therefore, programs aimed at vocational training, retraining, and job placement of women by regions need to be strengthened.

During the analysis, it was noted that between 2022–2023, more than 150,000 women were retrained at vocational training centers, and over 60 percent of them secured permanent employment. Positive experiences of such programs were observed in regions such as Tashkent province, Jizzakh, and Namangan. These programs have particularly broad coverage among young women and unemployed sisters, creating a sustainable source of income for them.

Additionally, positive results have been recorded in ensuring sustainable employment through the development of women's entrepreneurship. In particular, more than 350,000 women received loans, subsidies, and grants through the "Women's Register" between 2021–2024. These funds were mainly directed towards starting small businesses in sewing, food production, service provision, and agriculture.

Table 1. Female Employment Distribution by Sector in Uzbekistan (as of 2024, %)[11]

Sector	Female Employment (%)	Notes
Education	31%	The sector with the highest female employment
Healthcare	22%	Includes medical and caregiving professions
Services	18%	Beauty, trade, tourism services
Agriculture	16%	Mainly informal and seasonal jobs
Industry (light, food)	9%	Sewing, packaging, manufacturing
IT, Finance, Banking	4%	Technological and highly skilled sectors

The above table demonstrates that female employment in Uzbekistan is predominantly concentrated in traditional and socially "female-typical" sectors. Notably, the largest proportion of women—31 percent—are engaged in the education sector, which reflects both their inclination towards social services and prevailing occupational stereotypes. Significant shares are also observed in healthcare (22 percent) and services (18 percent), sectors characterized by relatively low wages and often unstable working conditions.

It is noteworthy that women's participation in high-income and technologically advanced sectors such as IT, finance, and banking amounts to only 4 percent, underscoring ongoing issues related to gender equality in professional fields. Additionally, the 16 percent female employment rate in agriculture largely corresponds to informal and seasonal work, leaving many women without adequate social protection.

Overall, there remains a pressing need to diversify female employment across various sectors and enhance their inclusion in technology-driven industries to foster sustainable economic growth.

Table 3. Economic Activity and Unemployment Rates of Women by Regions of Uzbekistan (As of Q1 2024) [12]

Region	Economically Active Women (%)	Female Unemployment Rate (%)	Remarks
Tashkent City	49%	8.2%	Dominance of urbanization and service sector
Andijan Region	43%	11.5%	Manufacturing and agriculture prevalent
Kashkadaryo Region	38%	12.9%	High share of informal employment
Navoi Region	46%	6.3%	Strong industrial and mining sectors
Samarkand Region	41%	10.4%	Limited employment sectors
Surkhandarya Region	36%	13.2%	Few permanent jobs available for women

Another important aspect is the negative influence of social norms and gender stereotypes on women's employment. According to interviews conducted, 38 percent of the participating women reported facing difficulties in going to work due to family or societal attitudes. This situation highlights the importance not only of economic factors but also of cultural and social approaches.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although policies aimed at ensuring sustainable employment for women have yielded positive results, existing issues such as regional disparities, occupational restrictions, and informal employment have not yet been fully resolved. This indicates the need for deeper integration of state policies, the application of gender-based analysis in planning, and the strengthening of intersectoral cooperation.

The sustainable employment of women is one of the decisive factors in the process of economic growth. Increasing women's participation in the labor market not only improves their socio-economic status but also contributes to the stable and inclusive development of society as a whole. Analyses show that the growth of women's employment serves as a key guarantee of economic efficiency, family well-being, and social stability.

At the same time, creating decent jobs for women, ensuring gender equality, improving working conditions, and expanding opportunities for vocational training remain urgent issues. Criteria for sustainable employment include wage equality, access to social protection, formal employment, safe working conditions, and opportunities for professional advancement.

When these criteria are fully met, women's potential can be fully realized, and their contribution to the economy significantly increases. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen systemic measures that promote women's employment within the framework of state policy and ongoing economic reforms.

To ensure sustainable growth in the future, it is crucial to develop new strategic approaches in the fields of the digital economy, social entrepreneurship, and vocational education related to women's employment.

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